

SHORT COMMUNICATION **OPEN ACCESS**

Multi-Rotor Systems: Can They Increase Economy-Wide Benefits Compared to Traditional Designs?

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Received: 25 June 2024 | **Revised:** 9 June 2025 | **Accepted:** 18 June 2025

Funding: This research was funded as part of the X-Rotor project which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme for Research and Innovation under Grant Agreement No. 101007135.

Keywords: computable general equilibrium | macroeconomic modelling | multi-rotor

ABSTRACT

This short communication reports on the economic consequences of increasing the market share of potentially lower-cost offshore wind designs. We use data on the projected levelised cost of energy (LCOE) for traditional horizontal axis wind turbine (HAWT) designs compared with an illustrative multi-rotor system which could have lower costs. Relative cost reductions are then introduced as improvements in productivity within the offshore wind generation sector in a computable general equilibrium model, exploring the economy-wide impacts of different market share scenarios. We find that, due to its potentially lower LCOE, increasing the share of multi-rotor designs in the United Kingdom would produce positive macroeconomic impacts, in terms of GDP and employment. Our findings suggest that there is merit in considering multi-rotor wind systems as part of a future energy strategy, and a methodology by which the economic outcomes of any potentially lower-cost technologies might be demonstrated.

1 | Introduction

Over the past decade, offshore wind development has surged, with global capacity increasing exponentially [1]. Currently, the predominant turbine design is the standard single rotor, three-bladed horizontal axis wind turbine (HAWT) design, originally perfected in onshore wind farms. However, as wind farms extend further offshore to harness larger wind resources, concerns have arisen regarding access issues and potential downtime in turbine output associated with single-rotor designs. Consequently, innovative turbine designs are now being explored to address these challenges. While these designs are expected to produce several technological and operational benefits, the focus of this paper is on their possible economy-wide benefits. Initial analysis for multi-rotor systems suggests that the LCOE could be lower—driven by their lower CAPEX and operations and maintenance (O&M) costs—and could produce lower electricity prices (compared with a system with only a single rotor) and with nearly

every industry reliant on electricity, this could drive economic activity linked to lower production costs.

One recent turbine design innovation is the multi-rotor concept which integrates vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT) and HAWT technologies into a combined system. This design allows turbines to continue producing output even if one or more rotor systems were to fail, albeit at a reduced capacity compared with full operation. This feature is particularly advantageous in challenging ocean environments like the North Sea, where access for O&M crafts can be difficult. Research suggests that one such multi-rotor design ('X-rotor') may potentially decrease O&M costs by up to 26% per GWh compared with traditional single-rotor three-bladed designs [2, 3]. These appear to offer the possibility, relative to HAWT designs, to dispose of the need for a gearbox or multipole generator—and reduce CAPEX costs, as well as significantly lowering O&M through easier access and reduced failures (and associated costs) [4, 5].

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The adoption of multi-rotor systems not only holds potential advantages for developers with more consistent returns and lower costs but also carries the potential for economy-wide benefits, including the prospect of reduced electricity prices. In this paper, we use cost reductions relative to HAWT projected for X-rotor systems as an illustrative case study as an example multi-rotor system to evaluate the economy-wide impacts of integrating multi-rotor technologies into offshore wind generation in the United Kingdom.¹

The correlation between economic development and renewable energy expansion has been extensively researched [6], with the most commonly cited connection being the positive impact of large-scale expenditures related to renewable energy investment, leading to increased job opportunities and heightened local economic activity [7]. Many studies employ *ex ante* (i.e., predictive) economic modelling techniques to assess economy-wide effects, including input–output (IO) and computable general equilibrium (CGE) analyses. Both approaches enable the measurement of the whole-economy effects associated with investments in renewables—beyond the initial spending associated with the projects themselves [8, 9]—and IO analysis has been used to analyse the substitution for fossil fuel generation in the electricity mix [10] and the environmental ramifications of renewable energy supply chains [11].

While IO analysis is undoubtedly a valuable tool for assessing economic impacts, it does have limitations, particularly its failure to account for supply-side responses, or inability to model the wider economic impact of cost reductions in specific technologies. This limitation may not significantly affect results when investments are small. However, with the global push towards achieving net-zero emissions and huge increases in global capacity of offshore wind capacity in the coming decades [12], future investments in renewables could significantly impact the supply side of the economy. To address this, some studies have used CGE models (e.g., [13, 14]). These models offer a more comprehensive understanding of the economy-wide effects of renewable energy investments, taking into account both demand and supply-side dynamics.

In addition to the above impacts, investment in renewable energy can also influence electricity prices, thus affecting the macroeconomy through the supply side directly. Lecca et al. [15] use a CGE framework to analyse how reductions in offshore wind could impact the UK economy through changes in expected electricity prices. In this paper, we develop a similar approach, exploring the economic consequences associated with a projected reduction in LCOE costs for a multi-rotor design compared with standard single-rotor designs. Our novelty, however, lies in the use of a CGE framework to quantify the potential economy-wide benefits of increasing market share of these potentially lower-cost systems.

2 | Model

CGE models are detailed representations of the economy that integrate economic data with economic theory. These models capture the interlinkages between firms, governments and households, as well as their interactions within goods, capital

and labour markets. Additionally, they account for external linkages through trade, migration and foreign investment. The economic data utilised to develop CGE models is derived from officially produced IO tables, which document the interactions within an economy over a specified period (typically 1 year). This economic data is amalgamated with a set of equations grounded in economic theory, aimed at capturing not only the underlying structure of the economy but also the behavioural responses of economic agents.

CGE models provide a comprehensive framework to simulate the economy-wide impacts of policy changes and trace their effects on different economic variables, including economic growth, exports, investment, employment and household income. These models have been employed by academics, governments and international organisations to evaluate the consequences of alternative policy choices.

One key advantage of CGE models for simulation is that they fully capture interactions between different actors in the economy, e.g., households and all industries, including the energy sector. This is particularly important for analysing the electricity sector, as almost all economic actors rely on electricity in some way, meaning any changes in the sector will have economy-wide effects. However, CGE models also have drawbacks, including high data requirements, modelling complexity and the assumption of market equilibrium.

The CGE model used in our analysis is the UKENVI model, based on the AMOS family of CGE frameworks. This model has been widely used to explore the connections between the economy, energy and the environment. Specifically, our model is calibrated on the 2018 Input–Output Table (IOT)² for the United Kingdom and encompasses 17 economic sectors, with nine electricity sectors. This level of detail on electricity generation technologies is not currently available in the published IO accounts for the United Kingdom, which only include a single aggregated electricity industry, encompassing all generation, transmission, distribution and trading activities. The published broad aggregation poses a significant challenge because it does not differentiate between the various methods of electricity generation and their distinct interactions with the economy. While this level of aggregation might suffice for purposes unrelated to electricity, our focus on generation—especially offshore wind—necessitates a disaggregation of the single electricity sector for our modelling purposes.

Various methods are available for separating generation within the electricity sector of the IOT. We adopt a ‘hybrid’ approach, combining ‘top-down’ assumptions for generation with ‘bottom-up’ data disaggregation, and we follow the method outlined in Connolly [16]. With the dataset and model calibrated with disaggregated electricity generation technologies, we can then use the model to analyse the economy-wide impact of cost reductions associated with multi-rotor turbines. Using the CGE approach, the reduction in LCOE for the offshore wind electricity generation sector acts as an economic stimulant on the macro level as it reduces prices throughout the economy. LCOE is not directly modelled in the CGE but is used as proxies for the costs of production in a sector, so that reduced costs relate to increased productivity of this generation technology. This is modelled as

an increase in (all factor) productivity in the offshore wind sector (i.e., enabling that sector to produce the same output with lower inputs, thus lowering costs). We model the cost reduction as a step change in electricity prices, and we present the long-run results (once the economy has reached a new equilibrium). For the labour market, the assumption is made that there is a fixed labour force, but employees have wage bargaining power.

We illustrate our methodology by comparing a multi-rotor system with standard, single-rotor, three-bladed turbines. To do so, we first gather estimates on the expected LCOE reduction in traditional HAWT wind turbines. BEIS (2020) estimates an LCOE of offshore wind in 2030 of £47/MWh. This is 17.5% below the current LCOE for offshore wind in the United Kingdom. The X-rotor multi-rotor system has been calculated to have an LCOE in 2030 of £40/MWh, representing a 29% reduction compared with current traditional designs [17, 18]. Our method means that we first carry out a counterfactual scenario with no multi-rotor market share in the UK's offshore wind sector and the improvement in productivity in the offshore wind sector to 2030³ coming only from refinements in HAWT designs and operation. To this, we add three further scenarios in which there is an increasing market share of potentially lower-cost X-rotor systems in the United Kingdom. Given the lack of reliable data on the potential market share, we have conducted simulations assuming market shares of 25%, 50% and 75%.

3 | Results

Table 1 reports the long-run results for key economic variables with the increase in offshore wind developments, including increases in the share of UK offshore wind from potentially lower-cost multi-rotor systems, with four simulations for sensitivity around the market share.

In line with previous studies, we find that, even with the small size of the industry relative to the overall UK economy, cost reductions in offshore wind could produce significant economy-wide impacts. Column 2 of Table 1 (corresponding

to a 0% multi-rotor system market share) is the counterfactual scenario which estimates the economy-wide benefits linked to the expected cost reduction in traditional three-bladed offshore wind designs. In this scenario, there is an increase in GDP of 0.19% coupled with a modest increase in total employment of 0.05%. The relatively larger increase in GDP than employment indicates that the sectors benefiting most from lower electricity prices, like manufacturing, are typically less dependent on labour inputs. Furthermore, Table 1 shows that lower electricity costs stimulate investment in the economy by 0.26% and increase real wages by 0.08%. This illustrates the broad economic advantages of reducing costs in the electricity sector (offshore wind sector).

In the final three columns of Table 1 we explore the potential economy-wide impacts if potentially lower-cost multi-rotor systems were to have a significant share of the offshore wind industry. Our findings suggest that increasing the presence of such systems in the UK's offshore wind capacity could yield additional benefits over systems that solely rely on traditional HAWT designs. Table 2 highlights the differences in economic impact between a scenario where 100% of the market consists of HAWTs and scenarios where the lower-cost system has a presence in the market (the columns in Table 2 can be calculated from the difference between the final three columns in Table 1 and the counterfactual results in the first column of Table 1). These differences underscore the potential for X-rotor technology to enhance the economic benefits of offshore wind development.

The simulation results for varying market shares follow a similar pattern to those of the 100% HAWT scenario, showing increases in GDP, employment, investment and real wages. A key finding of this paper is that increasing the market share positively impacts the overall economy. For instance, with a 25% market share there is a 0.01 percentage point increase in the long-run yearly employment compared with the 100% HAWT scenario. This increase rises to 0.09 percentage points when the market share reaches 75%. In absolute terms, this would be consistent with between 3240 (25% market share) and 13,210 (75% market

TABLE 1 | Economy-wide impacts linked to reduction in LCOE of offshore wind.

	Lower-cost multi-rotor system market share			
	0% (counterfactual)	25%	50%	75%
GDP income measure	0.19	0.23	0.30	0.39
Unemployment rate	-0.74	-0.90	-1.17	-1.49
Total employment	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.10
Nominal gross wage	0.15	0.19	0.25	0.33
Real gross wage	0.08	0.10	0.13	0.17
Real wage after tax	0.08	0.10	0.13	0.17
Replacement cost of capital	0.07	0.09	0.12	0.15
Households consumption	0.13	0.16	0.20	0.25
Net investment	0.26	0.32	0.41	0.51
Export	-0.08	-0.09	-0.12	-0.16

TABLE 2 | Comparison of lower-cost multi-rotor systems market share with counterfactual.

	Lower-cost multi-rotor system market share		
	25%	50%	75%
GDP income measure	0.04	0.11	0.20
Unemployment rate	-0.16	-0.43	-0.75
Total employment	0.01	0.02	0.05
Nominal gross wage	0.04	0.10	0.18
Real gross wage	0.02	0.05	0.09
Real wage after tax	0.02	0.05	0.09
Replacement cost of capital	0.02	0.05	0.08
Households consumption	0.03	0.07	0.12
Net investment	0.06	0.15	0.25
Export	-0.01	-0.04	-0.08

share) additional full-time-equivalent jobs annually. These enhanced economic impacts are attributed to the lower expected LCOE compared with traditional three-bladed HAWTs and underscore the economic benefits of integrating the lower-cost system into the UK's offshore wind capacity.

Our results make an additional contribution to the ongoing debate about the future of offshore wind developments. While we have used the X-rotor design as a case study, our findings apply to any lower-cost offshore wind design that offers a potentially lower levelised cost of energy (LCOE) than the designs currently in operation. From an industrial and developmental perspective, these multi-rotor designs could simplify the scaling up of offshore wind turbine capacity. Additionally, our analysis indicates that adopting such technologies could yield additional economic benefits.

4 | Conclusion

This short communication explores the potential macroeconomic benefits of integrating potentially lower-cost multi-rotor offshore wind designs into the UK electricity market with an increased market share. The economic advantages of offshore wind are well-documented, with the most common impact associated with investment and its role in driving economic activity. However, this study shifts the focus to the LCOE of multi-rotor systems compared with traditional designs and their impact on electricity prices, which in turn stimulates economic activity.

We use a CGE model to analyse the effects of a greater market share of multi-rotor systems compared with 100% HAWT designs. Our findings indicate that increased market share of multi-rotor systems can enhance economic activity, leading to higher long-run GDP and employment.

These results demonstrate that the potentially lower LCOE not only benefits developers but also aligns with the ambitions of

policymakers for the addition of offshore wind to contribute to economic development. It suggests that there should be a concerted effort to explore ways in which potentially lower-cost (including multi-rotor) systems can be promoted and integrated into the future electricity system, considering their positive impacts on the economy. This approach not only supports technological advancement but also facilitates a method to quantify the impacts of cost reductions in electricity generation on economic growth.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our gratitude to the two anonymous referees for their helpful comments. Their feedback has significantly improved the quality of our paper.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Peer Review

The peer review history for this article is available at <https://www.webofscience.com/api/gateway/wos/peer-review/10.1002/we.70045>.

Endnotes

- ¹Our methodology can be used to illustrate the economy-wide consequences of changes in the cost of any electricity technology relative to another of the same technology family. The specific figures in our report come from projected reductions in relative costs for LCOE relative to HAWT, and so are illustrative of the economy-wide consequences should such a cost reduction be realised.
- ²UK IO tables for 2018 were the most recent data available when this work commenced.
- ³McAuliffe et al. [17] use 2030 as the latest common year where there are HAWT LCOE estimates from BEIS 2020 and NREL [19]. Whether a reduction in LCOE exists in 2030 or 2035 does not change our modelling strategy. We show long-run results as we are focused on the total change and not the dynamics of the adjustment.

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